

**BRAND
GUIDELINES
DATA CELLAR**

BACKGROUND

DATA CELLAR aims to create a public energy dataspace that will support the creation, development, and management of LECs (Local Energy communities) in EU. DATA CELLAR will implement a collaborative platform providing an interoperable, modular, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets, Decision Support Tool, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) models to serve and support the spread LECs.

BRAND CONCEPTS

ENERGY

The brand has one main theme, energy. Create a database where energy forms are shared between communities. This energy flows, connects between different people and becomes, as these ideas generate new ones.

This is also characterised in the brand. Linear forms, which generate movement and continuous transformation and which connect with each other.

BRAND CONCEPTS

THE PEOPLE

They are the ones who share and receive the information, a project made for knowledge and the increase of new practices in the face of energy.

The logo generated for everyone, where there are no lower or upper case letters that define the tone or the information of the brand. It is characterised by being legible, dynamic and approachable.

DATA
CELLAR

PEOPLE

DATA CELLAR

ENERGY

CONNECTIONS

Presentation of the brand

Below we will show the visual
identity of the brand with the logo
in its different forms and versions
for placement on all adaptable
devices.

DATA CELLAR

DATA CELLAR

Construction and protection area

Construction and protection area

The brand and its reductions

DATA CELLAR

regular

reduction

Graphic elements

Below we will show the different graphic elements that make up the brand, which are directly linked to the concepts from which it arose: energy and people.

Typography

Typography for headlines
Typography for paragraphs

Color

Main color
Secondary colors

Graphic resources

Aa

BARLOW

Main typeface used for brand headlines, this typeface can be used both online and offline. It is a dry stick typeface that appears to have a condensed appearance. This will allow you to create standout headlines with ease and create a contrast with the logo and secondary typeface.

Aa

Aa

PLUS JAKARTA SANS

Secondary typography is a combination of legibility and dynamism. It can be used both for paragraph text and to support headlines and graphic elements.

Aa

MAIN COLOR

GRADIENT

SUSTAINABILITY
ENERGY

SECONDARY COLOURS

#00CD94

#00BFF8

#9152F6

#233B48

GRADIENTS COLOURS

Use correct

DATA CELLAR

Use correct

Use incorrect

DATA CELL

DATA CELLAR

Use incorrect

DATA CELLAR

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT

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